

DRIFT-WP2: A Curriculum for Managing Research Software Projects

This is a draft curriculum for managing Research Software Development. The focus is on the management side of such a project, highlighting key aspects to avoid project failures.

You can comment on this document via this link:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1p2O3ZRbZa73XixChkgxkgZSqp_i81hicshLHphGrzok/edit?usp=sharing

The target audience for this training include (but not limited to):

- Project and programme managers in research software environments (e.g., Universities, Research Institutes, etc.)
- Research Software Engineers (RSEs)
- Principal Investigators (PI) managing technical teams
- PhD and graduate students

This curriculum was constructed using a combination of consultation with members from the Research Software Engineering community and after examining open source and closed source similar training content. In particular, a special thanks to the following institutes and individuals for actively contributing content and for the feedback provided to produce this curriculum:

- University of Manchester (Dr Sarah Jaffa)
- Imperial College London (Dr Eirini Zormpa)
- University of Southampton (Dr Stephen Crouch)

In addition, a number of open source and closed sourced content were examined for inspiration and, where open source, re-use of relevant content is planned. In particular, the following online content were examined:

- [Managing Open Source Project Workshop](#)
- [Open Source 101 from the Linux Foundation](#)
- [Guide for Project Design](#)
- [Coderefinery Lessons](#)
- [Managing Research Software Project by Software Carpentry](#)
- [The Open Science Training Handbook](#)

We are interested in finding out from the community:

- Does this curriculum cover all the topics that you think are important for research software project managers (and their teams) to understand?
 - Are there any topics which are missing, or unclear?
 - Are there any topics that you consider less important, that should be optional or removed?
 - Are the learning objectives clear and appropriate?
- What other material do you know of that might be useful to implement this curriculum?
- What's the right delivery format? Is a five-day intensive course better than a series of shorter courses?
- How much effort/time are learners likely to be able to allocate to learning about project management?

Learning Objectives

- Understand distinct characteristics and challenges of research software projects.
 - Understand how research software development differs from commercial and enterprise software development
 - Identify typical challenges in managing research software projects within academic and research/scientific environments
- Apply fundamental project management concepts to Research Software Development
 - Define project scope, objectives and deliverables relevant to research outcomes
 - Use of lightweight but effective project plans, timeline and project milestones.
- How to build and sustain effective research software teams
 - Foster trust, collaboration and psychological safety within interdisciplinary teams
 - Design onboarding and mentoring processes that support long term team development
- Understand when to apply Agile Project Management methods
 - Use and adapt agile methods such as Scrum and Kanban to be flexible
 - Implement sprint cycles suitable for research environments
- When to use and participate in Open-Source research software projects
 - Apply best practices in Open-Source governance, community building and licensing
 - Setup and maintain open repositories with inclusive contribution guidelines and policies
 - Issues that can arise in Open-Source research software projects
- Plan and track project progress and resources
- Communicate and collaborate across roles and institutions
 - Facilitate effective team communication, stakeholder engagement and interdisciplinary coordination (e.g., via quarterly stakeholder meetings)
 - Use collaborative tools and documentation to support transparency and shared understanding
- Address common risks and quality concerns in research software
 - Continuous risk management
 - Issues tracking
- Address sustainability, reproducibility and required documentation of research software
 - Creating reproducible environments
 - Creating documentation that supports users, contributors and future maintainers

Course Modules

Each module is expected to take up between half a day to a full day. Full day modules will have some significant practical exercises (e.g., Scrum lecture). Estimates are provided within brackets in the module heading.

Module 1: Introduction to Research Software Project Management (half a day)

Presently, the content available online for this introductory level module is light and high-level. A good starting point would be the one available from (Tracy Teal) at [Managing Open Source Project Workshop](#). An overview of this workshop oriented content is available from <https://tracykteal.github.io/managing-os-project-workshop/> Even though this workshop related content covers some important aspects like setting up project goals, team/contributors, decision making, etc. it does not introduce the basic concept like what is research software, how does it compares to commercial software as well as project life cycle phases and many other important project management concepts.

Some useful open content is available from the course [Managing Research Software Project by Software Carpentry](#). This includes a brief introduction in bullet point form highlighting the difference between research software and “normal” software projects and what consists in a research software project. In addition, this course briefly covers Agile development, use of version control, issue trackers, code reviews, software testing, continuous integration, software license and software distribution. Some coverage of mentoring and building an organisation (i.e., turning a community into an organisation) is provided.

A description of open research software is available from [Open Research Software and Open Source](#). This additionally covers other open science aspects such as open access, open data, open reproducible research and evaluation, etc. Also, see the corresponding github repository, [The Open Science Training Handbook](#). This is an Open Educational resource available under the license <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>

Most of the content for this module would need to be produced from scratch.

- What is a Research Software Project?
 - Defining research software and its role in scientific discovery.
 - Is the research software to be made available as a product or service to external users (e.g., particular scientific communities) or whether it is for internal use by the technical team that is developing the software?
 - Differences between commercial software and research software (e.g., funding, stakeholders, requirements, lifespan, community engagement, sustainability).
- Why use Project Management to develop research software?
 - Common pitfalls in research software projects (scope creep, unmanaged expectations, etc.).
 - Benefits of structured project management.
- Key Project Management Concepts (Overview)
 - Project lifecycle phases (initiation, planning, execution, monitoring, closure).
 - Core components: Scope, Time, Cost, Quality, Resources, Risk, Communication, Stakeholders.
 - How above concepts and components map to research software development projects.

Module 2: Initiation, Planning and Scoping Research Software Projects (half a day)

No suitable content found online so far for this module. We may need to write most (if not all) of this content.

- Defining the project
 - Define the research problem and software solution
 - Create project objectives, success criteria and Minimum Viable Product (MVP)
 - Define what is in project scope and what is out
 - Taking over an existing / legacy project
- Stakeholder identification and management
 - Who are the stakeholders (researchers, funders, end-users, etc.)?
 - Identify and manage their expectations
 - How to keep stakeholders informed and engaged
- Capturing scientific/research requirements
 - Define methods for gathering requirements from the research community (interviews, workshops, surveys, etc.)
 - How to manage evolving and uncertain requirements
 - Prioritising key features for early impact
- Estimating Costs
 - Cost of personnel (e.g., developers, managers, scientific advisers)
 - Costs of software, hardware and Cloud services
 - Training and professional development costs
- Scheduling and resource planning
 - Roles, personnel and effort allocation
 - Workplan with milestones and deliverables
 - Gantt chart with timelines

Module 3: Agile and Iterative Methodologies (one day)

A lot of content for this is available from Manchester, UCL and Southampton universities. However, the content appears to be private and requires permission to re-use them.

An introduction to Scrum based Agile Software Development produced by University of Southampton is available from [Scrum Agile Development Process](#).

- Why Agile for Research Software development? (from Manchester University)
 - Embracing change and iteration in research
 - Core principles of agile development
- Introduction to Scrum (from [Scrum Agile Development Process](#))
 - Roles: Product Owner (researcher), Scrum Master, Development Team
 - Events: Sprints, Daily Scrums, Sprint Reviews, Sprint Retrospectives
 - Artifacts: Product Backlog, Sprint Backlog, Increment
- Introduction to Kanban (from Manchester University and UCL)
 - Visualizing workflow and limiting work-in-progress
 - Applicability for ongoing maintenance and small feature additions

- Choosing the right approach
 - When to use which methodology or a hybrid approach
- Tools:
 - Github project boards (e.g. from [GitHub for Project Management](#))
 - Jira?

Module 4: Team building, Trust and Onboarding (half a day)

No suitable content found online so far for this module. We may need to write most (if not all) of this content.

- Building high-functioning interdisciplinary team
- Establishing psychological safety and trust
- Onboarding contributors (e.g., peer-worker, mentorship)
- Information capture and knowledge exchange / transfer
- Inclusive communication across roles and cultures
- Tools: team handbooks, Slack/Teams etiquette

Module 5: Open-Source Development for Research Software (one day)

A significant amount of open source content for this is available from [OpenScienceMOOC - Module 5: Open Research Software and Open Source](#)

More tools related content for open source software is available from [Tools for Managing Open Source Programs](#)

Linux foundation provides [Recommended Practices for Hosting and Managing Open Source Projects on GitHub](#)

- Why open source? Benefits, risks, and obligations in research
 - When open source is not suitable(i.e., a project has to be closed source and private)
- Choosing the right license (MIT, BSD, GPL, etc.)
- Setting up public repos: README, issue templates, community files
- Running inclusive and well governed Open-Source project
- Managing external contributions and community participation
- Tools: GitHub/GitLab, Code of Conduct, GitHub Discussions

Module 6: Project Execution and Monitoring (half a day)

Mostly, no suitable content found online so far for this module. While there are plenty of resources for version control / testing / debugging / documentation, they do not concentrate on how this relates to project management. We may need to write most of this content.

- Managing the Development Process
 - Facilitate and monitor team collaboration and communication
 - Regular progress tracking and troubleshooting issues
 - Managing software releases

- Communication and Reporting
 - Regular updates to stakeholders
 - Highlight progress, challenges and next steps
- Best practices for version control
- Best practices for software testing and debugging
- Documentation strategies for research software
 - [Documenting research software in engineering science](#)

Module 7: Risk Management and Quality Assurance (half a day)

For this module, we will have to adapt general risk management and quality assurance from project management theories and practices to Research Software development.

- Identify Risks in the project
 - Technical risks (e.g., changing requirements, software integration issues, etc.)
 - Project risks (e.g., personnel availability, infrastructure issues, funding delays, etc.)
 - Research specific risks (e.g., unexpected scientific results/findings, emergence of new better scientific methods, etc.)
- Risk Assessment and Mitigation Strategies
 - Why do research software projects go wrong?
 - Analyse likelihood and impact
 - Develop contingency plans
- Ensuring Research Software Quality
 - Reproducibility of results
 - Code readability and maintainability
 - Tools and practices

Module 8: Project Closure and Sustainability (half a day)

No suitable content found online so far for this module. We may need to write most (if not all) of this content.

- Project Completion and Handover
 - Verifying project objectives are met
 - Formalizing project completion
 - Handing over software and documentation to research community or maintenance team
- Lessons Learned and Retrospectives
 - Analysing what went well and what could be improved
 - Capturing knowledge for future projects
- Sustainability of Research Software
 - Strategies for long-term usability and maintenance
 - Archiving, publication, and citation of research software

References

1. Managing Open Source Project Workshop,
<https://github.com/tracykteal/managing-os-project-workshop>
2. Open Source 101 from the Linux Foundation,
<https://lfenergy.org/learn-open-source-best-practices-with-these-free-resources/>
3. Guide for Project Design,
<https://book.the-turing-way.org/project-design/project-design>
4. Coderefinery Lessons,
<https://coderefinery.org/lessons/#lessons-that-we-teach-in-our-tools-workshops>
5. Managing Research Software Project by Software Carpentry,
<https://swcarpentry.github.io/managing-research-software-projects/>
6. Open Research Software and Open Source,
https://open-science-training-handbook.github.io/Open-Science-Training-Handbook_EN/02OpenScienceBasics/03OpenResearchSoftwareAndOpenSource.html
7. Scrum Agile Development Process,
<https://southampton-rsg-training.github.io/industry-skills-agile-training/26-agile-development-process.html>
8. OpenScienceMOOC - Module 5: Open Research Software and Open Source,
https://github.com/OpenScienceMOOC/Module-5-Open-Research-Software-and-Open-Source/blob/master/content_development/MAIN.md
9. Tools for Managing Open Source Programs,
<https://todogroup.org/resources/guides/tools-for-managing-open-source-programs/>
10. Recommended Practices for Hosting and Managing Open Source Projects on GitHub,
<https://project.linuxfoundation.org/hubfs/LF%20Research/Recommended%20Practices%20for%20Hosting%20and%20Managing%20OS%20Projects%20on%20Github%20-%20Report.pdf?hsLang=en>
11. Documenting research software in engineering science,
<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-022-10376-9>
12. The Open Science Training Handbook,
https://github.com/Open-Science-Training-Handbook/Open-Science-Training-Handbook_EN

13. GitHub for Project Management workshop for ByteSizedRSE:
[Repository](#) [Intro slides](#) [Tutorial slides](#) [Code for Thought podcast episode](#)
- 14.